

Integrated Resource Management for Sustainable Agricultural Land Use Plan in Hisar District Using Geo-Informatics- A Case Study

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Abstract: The present study is based on the uses of qualitative and quantitative data for sustainable management of natural resources (soil, underground water quality, depth of water table etc.) with the aims to analyze the authentication of present land use in the context of sustainability of agriculture. The productivity level of rice, cotton, wheat, mustard and gram crops is showing a declining trend, despite manifolds increase in fertilizer use and plant protection chemicals in the study area. Sustainable agricultural practices fulfill the demand of coming generation and increasing population in respect to the sustainability of natural resources. The study suggested that 700.83, 18.57, 123.92 square kilometer of the study area is recommended for agri-horticulture crops, agro forestry and for double crop with clone eucalyptus plantation on field boundary, 119.98 square kilometer area is recommended for horticulture plantation with drip irrigation and 2340.57 square kilometer area is recommended for existing cropping system with good agriculture management practices with soil and water conservation measures.

Keywords: Sustainable agriculture, Satellite data, Remote sensing, GIS, Landuse recommendation

The agriculture system which encompasses the interactions of physical, biological, technical and socio-economic factors, some of which are under human control, for the purpose of producing food, the agro-ecological entity. The agro-ecosystem, therefore, is considered to be in equilibrium with environmental and management factors, which produce a sustained yields. Today with emphasis on quick production, the optimum balance between the use of land/soil resources and agro-production conditions are disturbed. Thus, the productivity level of different crops, has either reached at plateau level or showing declining trend, despite manifolds increase in fertilizer use and plant protection chemicals. Farmers here continue to grow rice-wheat and cotton - wheat as dominant crops due to government incentives and market price ignoring the suitability of soil, water and climatic conditions. The inappropriate land use and introduction of canal irrigation have resulted in soil degradation, soil erosion, salinity & alkalinity and waterlogging, besides nutrient losses as well as depletion of ground water at an alarming rate. The problems of salinity, sodicity and waterlogging have been attributed to irrigation without providing drainage.

It may seem like an economic boost for a few decades, but the environmental damage is permanent because agricultural land use pattern will consume the soil and water resources. Present agricultural practices are based on the monoculture and there is lack of crop diversification. The present study evaluated the utilization of the land resources

with reference to natural resource characteristics and land use pattern and also examined the sustainability performance of current land use types with reference to land resources.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Indian Remote Sensing satellite Series (LISS-III) satellite data for the years 2017-18 was used for interpretation of the existing landuse / land cover, cropping pattern and crop rotation. The projection system and datum for geo-referencing of the satellite images were taken as World Geodetic System 84 and Universal Transverse Mercator projection respectively (UTM). Data related to soil series and maps were collected from HARSAC with their physical and chemical properties. Data related to underground water depth and quality is collected from Central Ground Water Board, Ministry of Water Resources, Government of India. Toposheets of Survey of India were used for defining locations of villages, transport network, cultural features, canal network and demarcation of major & minor towns/ cities. Climatic data, published literature, maps and reports were collected, consulted and used pertinent. Arc GIS Desktop 9.3 (Integration and overlay analysis) ERDAS Imagine 9.3, (geo-referencing) and Geometrica 10.3 (digital classification) software were used.

The study is mainly concerned to develop and suggest sustainable agricultural land use plan for the study area based on existing resources such as soils, cropping pattern,

ground water table depth, ground & surface water quality and present land use. Satellite images were used after image rectification and suitable image enhancements technique will be applied to facilitate the delineation and interpretation of different thematic information. Visual interpretation method was used to prepare pre-field interpreted map. The satellite data is interpreted based on image interpretation elements like tone, texture, size, shape, pattern, aspect, association etc. Suitable field sampling will be used to assess the interpreted elements and relate with satellite data. The field data collections are aided by GPS in order to locate the ground verification points on the image and for further incorporation of detail. Integrating ground water resources map was prepared using interpolation techniques in GIS environment. Water table deepness maps for pre monsoon and post monsoon with water quality and draping of depth to water table map in GIS environment.

The GIS and remote sensing software was used for analysing the spatial distribution of the various aspects taken up for study. GIS techniques were used in order to create layers of present land use/ land cover. All these layers were overplayed in Arc GIS desktop 9.3 software and a common or single layer is generated using all above layers through union command. This single layer has all information like soils, water quality, water table depth; present land use/ land cover for each and every polygon. Based on these layers characteristics such as soil type and texture, physiographic unit, underground water quality, underground water depth, type of present land use and land cover; a final recommendation is given to each and every polygon. These layers were put in GIS format to create the database. On the basis of database pre land use recommendation were suggested.

The sustainable agricultural land use plan has been prepared by integrating different thematic maps with socio-economic conditions. These thematic maps were analyzed in term of resources potential and limitations individually and jointly. For recommending sustainable agricultural land use action plan various decision rules have been formulated. Based on decided rules and integration of all thematic maps, land resources action plan has been explained. Major suggested recommendations for management of agricultural land are agro-horticulture, agro forestry, agro forestry with dry land crops management, double crop, crop diversification with suitable soil conservation measures and agri horticulture with suitable soil conservation measures. The management of wastelands includes forest plantation for scrubland, silvi pasture for degraded pastures and leveling and dune stabilization for sand dunal areas.

As per decision rules, a short discussion was complete

on utility and sustainability of current land use pattern particularly in context of agricultural construction and quality of ecosystem. Later on, the suitability of these existing practices were examined and various alternative land use activities like agro horticulture, agro forestry, agro forestry with improved dry land crops management, double crop, silvi pasture, leveling & dune stabilization have been considered. For recommending these package & practices, the basic research activity of CCS, HAU, Hisar (Rabi & Kharif Faslon Ki Samagra Sifarasen, HAU, Hisar) and ICAR with latest technologies of agriculture research and development were considered in the district.

Study area: The location of the district is 28°53'45" to 29°49'15" North latitude and 74°5'13'15" to 76°18'15" East longitude having 3983 square kilometers area. It has surrounded by Fatehabad and Jind districts of Haryana in north east and north respectively. The climate of the area is famous for its waterlessness and boundaries of hotness with insufficient rainfall and varies arid to semi arid type. It is sub-tropical, monsoonic and continental. The average annual rainfall in the district is 307.7 mm which usually increases towards south west to north east direction. Near about 65% of the yearly rainfall arrived in rainy season (July to September). Physiographically, the study area consists of alluvial plain, flood plain, aeolian plain and fluvio aeolian plain in which dune complexes exist. The main soils in the area varies from loamy to clay loamy in low lying plain, sandy loam to loamy in nearly level plain and sand to loamy sand in aeolian plain. Situated in the northwest, Hisar is one of the leading agriculture district of the state whereas 132.89 square kilometres area of the district is under wastelands that is 3.34 percentage to the total geographical area of the district. It is also the most intensively cultivated with 193% (statistical abstract of Haryana, 2017) cropping intensity. It covers 3983 square kilometres area with a population of 1,743,931 persons (Census of India, 2011).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Different thematic maps like land use / land cover, soils family, soil sub group, soil texture, soil available water holding capacity map, water quality and depth, cropping pattern and rotation coupled with socio-economic and agro-climatic data were integrated to suggest suitable combinations of practices for various agricultural land use parcels. In formulation of action plan remaining land use/land cover and wastelands have been taken as basis for assessing the present land use and to suggest alternative sustainable agricultural land use suitability.

Soil resources: Eleven soil series have been observed in the district that are Kharia, Bichpari, Ratia, Bas, Fatehpuri,

Fig. 1. Methodology Flow Chart

Kanala, Dabra, Gangwa, Jundli Khurd, Dhingsra and Niyana. Above all soil series are classified according to Soil Taxonomy. It was observed that four types soil texture family classes (Coarse loamy, Fine loamy, Fine and Sandy) are existing in the district. Fine loamy class covers 2076.56 square kilometers area that is 49.79 % of the district. Mainly this class is found in eastern part of the study area in Narnaund, Uklana, Hansi-I, Hansi-II and Hisar-I blocks. Second largest class is coarse loamy that covers 1570.67 square kilometers area which is 37.66 % of the district. This class is dispersed in western part of the study area in Adampur, Hisar-II and Agroha blocks. Third largest class is sandy that covers 259.08 square kilometres area which is 6.21 % of the study area and founded in scattered patches in whole district. Other class is fine which covers only 2.80 square kilometers.

Ground water quality status: The overall ground water prospects of the district vary from poor to excellent. The units of alluvial origin have very good to excellent underground water scenarios but on the other hand, ground water prospects in aeolian plain and sand dunal areas are moderate and poor respectively. Alluvial plain with sand have good ground water potential. The ground water quality of study area is good to saline. These include fresh water (38.11 %), sub marginal (40.00%) marginal (18.44%) and saline (3.45%). It was observed that adjacent to water body like

canal, ponds and river; the sub surface water quality is good.

Ground water table depth status: The depth of underground water table in the study area is lying between 1.5 to >15 meters below ground level (BGL) in various parts. The 96 percent of total area falls under the depth zone of 1.5 to >15 meters below ground level during pre monsoon. Highest depth of water table observed in surrounding Balsamand village. Near about fifty eight to sixty percent of the study area in pre monsoon season falls under 5-10 meter depth (2510.83 square kilometres) followed by 10-15 meter depth (958.49 square kilometres). The depth which is considered critical and falls under waterlogged category (Pre monsoon) is between 0-1.5 meter and covers an area of 8.76 square kilometers.

Land use / land cover: Land use and land cover map has been generated by visual interpretation of satellite images of October 2017 and March 2018. The land use of the study area has been broadly categorized into built up land, agriculture, wastelands and water bodies. The landuse statistics reveals that major land use in this area is agriculture, which covers 3877.12 square kilometres including double crop, rabi only, kharif only and current fallow class. The double cropped area under agriculture land use constitutes 80.89 percent of total area. The study indicated a moderate intensity of cropping of 191.92 percent. The wasteland categories viz. degraded pastures, scrublands and sands comprises of only 3.65

percent of the study area. Built-up land use categories occupy 8 percent of total area and rest of area is covered by water bodies. It is concluded that area under input intensive crops of green revolution has increased at the cost of traditional crops and desi cotton, gram, pulses and millets cropped area have declined significantly. Due to these input intensive agriculture, the area is suffering from decreasing water table, excessive use of fertilizers and pesticides from primary to serious ecological difficulties.

Cropping pattern: *Rabi* and *Kharif* are the main two cropping seasons in the study area. *Kharif* crop season starts in May-June and continues upto September- October. Remote Sensing data of *Kharif* season (September -2017) estimated that the Cotton, Sugarcane, Rice, Bajra/Jowar/Guar and other crops occupied 1660.20, 0.53, 773.83 and 280.33 square kilometres area correspondingly. In *rabi* season (March 2018) wheat crop sown in 2131.25 square kilometers area, followed by mustard (686.32 square kilometers) and pulses (146.67 square kilometers). The study has exposed that there is serious need for diversification of cropping pattern. The area is also facing another problem of complete absence of natural forest, therefore; there is urgent need of forest plantation on wastelands community land, government land and along with transport network and irrigation channels to restore ecological balance of the study area.

Development of agricultural land use plan: Agricultural land resources management has emerged as one of most important issue to improve agricultural productivity and sustainability through protection and rational consumption of our natural resources base like water, soil, vegetation,

livestock and genetic diversity. Sustainable agricultural land use plan was developed for the study area and different agricultural land use recommendations were suggested. Agri- horticulture is suggested in 806.92 square kilometres that was 20.23% of the total recommended area. Agri horticulture class included different sub classes that are Agri horticulture after land leveling, Agri horticulture with mixing of tube well and canal water, Agri horticulture with crop diversification required, Agri Horticulture with eucalyptus plantation on field boundary and Agri horticulture with salt tolerant species.

Recommendation related to horticulture plantation (including Horticultural plantation/ Silvi pasture, Horticulture plantation for panchayat income or on contract, Horticulture plantation with drip irrigation, Horticulture plantation with drip irrigation adopting rainwater harvesting/ surface water / water tank purifier) occupied 186.22 square kilometers area that was 4.67% of the total recommended area. Agro forestry class recommended in 227.57 square kilometres that was 5.71% of total recommended area. Agro forestry activity involve Agro Forestry / Fodder dairy cattle, Agro forestry after land leveling, Agro forestry with dry farming, Agro forestry/ forest plantation, Agro forestry with salt tolerant tree species and Agro forestry with bio drainage. Like that, Double crop recommended class occupies total area of 127.33 square kilometers which was 3.19 percent of total recommended area. This class include Double crop after land leveling or double crop with sprinkler irrigation, Double crop with clone eucalyptus plantation on field boundary, Double crop with drain out sub classes. Area wise suggested agricultural land use recommendations are displayed in Table 1 and spatial distribution of different

Fig. 2. Spatial distribution of different suggested environmentally sound agricultural land use

Table 1. Area under different suggested agricultural land use recommendation

Suggested agricultural land use recommendation	Area in square kilometres	Total geographical area (%)
Afforestation/Silvi pasture with soil & water conservation measures	37.84	0.95
Clone eucalyptus on field boundary	0.91	0.02
Agri horticulture	700.83	17.58
Agri horticulture after land levelling	1.38	0.03
Agri horticulture with mixing of tubewell and canal water	50.28	1.26
Agri horticulture with salt tolerant species	24.48	0.61
Agro forestry	183.57	4.60
Agro Forestry / Fodder dairy cattle	30.16	0.76
Agro forestry after land levelling	0.18	0.00
Agro forestry with dry farming	5.99	0.15
Excess fresh water potential zone for pipelines	0.47	0.01
Bio drainage/Aquaculture/ saline aquaculture	44.45	1.11
Clone eucalyptus on embankment plantation	16.31	0.41
Conservation of forest and gap filling	2.19	0.05
Double crop after land levelling or double crop with sprinkler irrigation	3.39	0.08
Double crop having water conserving crops	17.13	0.43
Double crop with clone eucalyptus plantation on field boundary	123.92	3.11
Double crop with crop diversification	10.56	0.26
Double crop with drain out	0.02	0.00
Double crop with soil and water conservation measures	7.86	0.20
Existing cropping system with good agriculture management practices with soil and water conservation measures	2340.57	58.70
Existing system with salt tolerant species	0.14	0.00
Agro forestry/ forest plantation	1.23	0.03
Bio drainage	0.33	0.01
Horticultural plantation/ Silvi pasture	11.04	0.28
Horticulture plantation for panchayat income or on contract	30.68	0.77
Salt tolerant forest plantation/ bio drainage	40.49	1.02
Horticulture plantation with drip irrigation	119.98	3.01
Horticulture plantation with drip irrigation adopting rainwater harvesting/ surface water / water tank purifier	24.52	0.61
Pisciculture	2.27	0.06
Agri Horticulture with eucalyptus plantation on field boundary	1.13	0.03
Social and community forestry/ MPTS	22.26	0.56
Agri horticulture with crop diversification required	28.82	0.72
Agro forestry with salt tolerant tree species	77.68	1.95
Saline aquaculture on embankment plantation	1.37	0.03
Agro forestry with bio drainage	6.44	0.16
Pulses and oilseed crops	16.76	0.42
Grand Total	987.65	100.00

suggested environmentally sound agricultural land use recommendations is displayed in Figure 2.

CONCLUSIONS

Presently there is urgent need of integrated land & water resources development and crop diversification plans for sustainable agriculture development. This crop diversification plan has considered the climate, existing soils, irrigation facilities, mechanization and socio-economic factors. The potential benefits of natural resources development plan in the form of increased production of food grains, oil seeds, pulses, fruits and vegetables. The increased fodder production correspondingly increases livestock products. The natural resources development plans will also help to generate employment opportunity and improve economic and nutrition standard of the people. This resources development plan will improve over all environmental conditions of area in form of saving the land from degradation, improve the soil fertility increasing the area under irrigation and reducing the impact of drought.

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